

A child-friendly school: How the school implements the model

Somariah Fitriani¹, Istaryatiningtias², Lelly Qodariah³

^{1,2}Department of Educational Administration, University of Muhammadiyah Prof. DR. HAMKA, Indonesia

³Department of Historical Education, University of Muhammadiyah Prof. DR. HAMKA, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received May 29, 2020

Revised Dec 6, 2020

Accepted Jan 27, 2021

Keywords:

Child-friendly school

Children's rights

Learning environment

Quality education

ABSTRACT

The study was to examine the implementation of child-friendly school (CFS) in a public elementary school. This study employed a single case study method, as Public Elementary School of Ragunan 01 is the unit of research analysis. The school has been declared as a child-friendly school since 2015. The quantitative data generated, however, were only used to see the percentage of the characteristics of CFS model. Thus, the data were gathered through observation, questionnaires and interviews to obtain more comprehensive empirical data. The questionnaire was distributed to all teachers and 15 class coordinators of students' parents to obtain data about the implementation of CFS. Interviews were conducted with several important multi-stakeholders identified. The results showed that thirteen characteristics of the CFS had been implemented well with a percentage value above 95%. It indicates that this school has been able to realize the CFS model following its principles. Besides, the school has met the requirement of the six essential components of CFS adapted according to Indonesian educational contexts. It indicates that the implementation of CFS is in accordance with the concept of UNICEF but with some differences.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Somariah Fitriani

Department of Educational Administration

University of Muhammadiyah Prof. DR. HAMKA

Jalan Warung Buncit Raya No 17, Pancoran Jakarta Selatan, Indonesia

Email: somariah@uhamka.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

Learning in a pleasant atmosphere is one of the top priorities in schools, especially for primary education as Barrow and Woods [1] found out that "the object of schooling is not to" transmit a body of knowledge "but to encourage students to" love learning for its own sake. In other words, the school's primary purpose is to make students enjoy learning for their interests, in which the school and its educators must create a pleasant atmosphere. Prior studies have revealed that a learning environment is a significant variable that generally affects student learning [2-4]. Vermeulen, *et al.* [5] reported that the learning environment makes students more motivated, which, in turn, increases their learning outcomes. Besides, enjoyable learning aims to lead to quality education that does not discriminate students in terms of religion, race, gender, skin color, and language. The quality of education, according to UNICEF, is an education that works for every child and allows all children to attain their full potential [6]. The quality of education itself is related to the quality of teaching and learning that can be achieved through a positive and supportive school organization climate [7]. Therefore, enlightening and refining quality education must be put into one of the worldwide agendas for all countries to support education for all and eradicate the discrimination between boys and girls, racism, bullying, and verbal and non-verbal violence. To address this issue, a CFS model has become the dominant instrument that UNICEF advocates for and promotes quality education.

Since students, particularly elementary school children, experience both positive and negative conditions in school. The schools are required to implement a child-friendly environment. A child friendly environment, in the words of Horelli [8], is complex, multidimensional and multilevel, which also refers to an environmental framework supporting the individual child and the associated groups that are important for the child. Therefore, a comprehensive concept in the curriculum of learning in schools is needed to minimize negative experiences and embrace children to reach their full potential as it is written in the millennium development goals (MDGs). One of its goals for education is to achieve universal primary education [9]. The UN Development Program has also estimated that 90% of children in developing regions have primary schooling now, and gaps between girls and boys have diminished [10]. Meeting MDGs related to education requires not only putting all children into school but ensuring that all schools work in the best interests of the children entrusted to them. It means providing a safe and protective school that has adequate staff with trained teachers, is equipped with adequate resources, and is blessed with appropriate conditions for learning is a top priority. Thus, a comprehensive concept is needed to achieve positive and supportive experiences for children of primary age education in school. The CFS model approach is a comprehensive concept that has so far been implemented in various countries. UNICEF [6] reported that about 56 countries had applied this model until 2007 with various interpretations, which is likely due to each country's local wisdoms or local educational contexts. The framework of CFS is motivated by a philosophy of children's rights, which considers the role of school to facilitate the development of the whole child [11].

In Indonesia, the project of CFS initiated in 2015 was created to reform an educational process focusing on child-center activities instead of teacher-center activities and to reduce the incidents of bullying in schools. In addition, the existence of CFS is inseparable from the program to develop child-friendly cities where 31 children's rights are fulfilled. CFS is one of the crucial indicators of the evaluation of child-friendly cities. Thus, the model of CFS is also one of the Indonesian government programs to realize children's rights. Referring to the concept of UNICEF, CFS is defined as a program to create safe, clean, healthy, caring, and cultured environmental conditions, which can guarantee the fulfillment of children's rights and protection from violence, discrimination, and another mistreatment. It supports children's participation, especially in planning, policy, learning, and supervision [12]. Moreover, the CFS model is an approach that encourages schools to work in the interests of children, where educated teachers provide a safe, healthy and protective environment; with adequate resources and physical, emotional and social conditions for learning; protect children's rights; have a learning context that allows children to learn and develop; respect the identity, interests, and needs of children [13].

On account of such a concept and its aim, creating a positive learning environment is highly essential to pursue a quality education and students' quality. Küçüker, *et al.* [14] pointed out that it is imperative to create an environment, which is appropriate for its purpose. It is also vital to analyze the learning environment with proper methods, identify the insufficiencies, and develop the learning environment. In the word of Fraser [15], he emphasized that investigations into the relations between the characteristics of the learning environment and pupil outcomes have been testified as to the most popular setting of research within the particular research field. The creation of this CFS climate is essential based on the pattern of people's school life experiences and reflects norms, goals, values, interpersonal relationships, teaching and learning practices, and organizational structure [16]. UNESCO in the year of 2001 reported that a positive environment and quality education are the main traits of CFSs. Based on previous comparative research conducted in CFSs and conventional schools, the study found that CFSs have a better learning environment and academic achievement than conventional schools [17]. In addition, an experimental study showed that CFS has a positive effect on students' metacognitive thinking skills as well [18].

The CFS model's implementation is different in each country around the world. The differences are likely due to different cultural background, local wisdom, perspectives and other significant factors. The research shows that the characteristics of CFS change according to the school's socioeconomic level, student sex, and grade level [19]. The CFS model that focuses on its characteristics and six essential components, namely pedagogy, health, gender sensitivity, community participation, inclusiveness, and protection developed by UNICEF, needs to be examined more holistically, especially in elementary school settings. Previous studies in the domain of CFSs have demonstrated the effectiveness of learning environment and academic achievement. However, our review of the literature suggests that there have been very few studies that have examined the characteristics of CFS in general, and in the domain of components of CFS. Thus, to fill the gap in the literature, the research focuses on the characteristics of rights-based CFS and six essential components in Indonesian context and to examine the fundamental differences with the component developed by UNICEF.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Research design

The study adopted single case study to examine the implementation of CFS model in terms of the characteristics and the components of CFS model. This single case study emphasized more on qualitative approach, thus the data generated were mostly qualitative. The quantitative data generated, however, were only used to gather the data and see the percentage of the characteristics of CFS model. The data interpretations of six components of CFS were obtained by using qualitative approach, in which it relies entirely on human perception and understanding. Such research is also defined as interpretive research [20] since it uses more interpretations from researchers than research approaches quantitatively. The study of the qualitative approach employed a case study method with a single case holistic design, in which the information gathering was primarily carried out in Public Elementary School of Ragunan 01, Jakarta, Indonesia as a unit analysis is a small group of a school [21-23]. According to Gall, *et al.* [24], four features of a case study include: (a) an in-depth study of (b) one or more of phenomena examples (c) in the milieu of their actual life and (d) representing the involvements of the phenomenon participants.

2.2. Participants

The quantitative and qualitative data of the research were gathered from the Public Elementary School of Ragunan 01, which is located in South Jakarta, Indonesia. The school has implemented the model of CFS since 2015, which its standard is somewhat different due to several factors. There are 23 teachers and 15 students' parents of class coordinators took part to fill the questionnaire. To obtain more information about the implementation of CFS, the researchers interviewed principal, vice principals, several teachers, a coordinator of the school committee, students' parents, school operator, and several students of grade 4, 5 and 6 whom the researcher met during the break time. In this qualitative research, a purposive sampling technique was used in sampling as the researcher deliberately chose individuals and research sites to study or understood the main phenomena [25].

2.3. Data collection and data analysis

The research was conducted for three months in which the researchers visited the schools three to four times a week for about three hours each. For data collection, the researchers relied on direct observation, in-depth interviews of an open-ended question, and documentary analysis. Besides, the researchers also did note taking and took pictures during data collection. The things that we observed are school infrastructure, school environment, the learning process, the canteen, library, and the behavior of students in class and outside the classroom, especially during breaks and the rapport between teachers and students in the class. The researcher recorded each event, documented it, and recorded the interview so as not to miss the information provided to the researchers. During the observation, the researchers were outside the classroom and took notes, photographed, and recorded conversations and learning processes between the teacher and students. Its aim was not to disrupt the learning process, and the teacher stayed natural without feeling researched. Also, researchers checked extracurricular activities, facilities such as prayer rooms, libraries, a school health clinic, teacher's room, principal's room, bathroom, and canteen. Interviews with school principals, deputy principals and teachers, and other staff were conducted formally in the room, while interviews with school committee heads, students' parents, and some students were conducted informally in a relaxed atmosphere. The researchers made an appointment in advance through WhatsApp and met with the head of the school committee outside the classroom, such as the canteen and restaurant. Interviews with students were conducted during school breaks in the school garden canteen. The researchers also made a phone call to the previous headmaster to obtain more information related to the previous implementation of CFS under his leadership.

The questionnaire of the 13 characteristics is adopted from UNICEF [13, 26] and the six components are adopted from the CFS guidance book [12]. The 13 characteristics include: 1) Reflects and realizes the rights of every child; 2) Sees and understands the whole child, in a broad context; 3) Child-centered; 4) Gender-sensitive and girl-friendly; 5) Promotes quality learning outcomes; 6) Provides education based on the reality of children's lives; 7) Flexible and responds to diversity; 8) Acts to ensure inclusion, respect, and equality of opportunity for all children; 9) Promotes mental and physical health; 10) Provides education that is affordable and accessible; 11) Enhances teacher capacity, morale, commitment, and status; 12) Focus on family; and 13) Community-based school. The components of CFS model are: 1) A written commitment as a policy; 2) Implementation of a child-friendly learning process; 3) Well-trained teachers and personnel on children's rights; 4) Child-friendly facilities and infrastructure; 5) Children's participation; and 6) Parent participation, community institutions, business world, other stakeholders, and alumni. The characteristics and the components of CFS play an imperative role in understanding the CFS model and the evaluation of CFS implementation at schools.

The data analysis of qualitative method adopted the Miles and Hubberman model, including data reduction, data display, and conclusion. To reduce the data of observations and interviews, the researchers selected the data by classifying and coding all information based on similar sub-themes. The data were then interpreted and written in the table. However, the questionnaire's data were analyzed by using the percentage in the form of a table. The researcher employed data source triangulation and methodological triangulation for the validity and reliability of the data. Method triangulation was carried out to verify the data obtained from observations, interviews, and documents. In contrast, the source triangulation was done to ensure the accuracy of the data obtained not only from one source but crosschecks with other sources related to research questions and research topics.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study mainly intended to focus on the implementation of CFS model in terms of the characteristics and six components, which became valuable parts in the research findings. The characteristics and the components of CFS become significant instruments to elaborate the implementation of CFS model in schools which the objective is to assess whether the school has understood the concepts of CFS model and run its model well. Thus, the aims of the study were to seek the significant differences when adopting the CFS model in Indonesian's perspective. The data were obtained from various participants as it is shown in Table 1. The demographic data of the participants include the teachers and the representative of class coordinators when filling the questionnaire on the characteristics of CFS. Below findings are also based on the interviews with previous headmaster, current headmaster, several teachers and other staff that the researchers met during school visit. The other participants are the students of grade 4, 5, and 6 who answered the questions about the components of CFS as to obtain the information about their feelings and their perspectives on CFS implementation.

Table 1. The demographic data of participants

Characteristics	Description	The number of teachers	Percentage	The number of class coordinators	Percentage
Gender	Male	7	30.44	-	-
	Female	16	69.56	15	100
Age	21-30	2	8.70	-	-
	31-40	11	47.84	8	53.33
	41-50	5	21.73	7	46.67
	51-60	5	21.73	-	-
	More than 61	-	-	-	-
The education level	Elementary school	-	-	1	6.7
	Junior high school	-	-	2	13.3
	Senior high school	-	-	10	66.7
	The diploma I/II/III	-	-	2	13.3
	Bachelor degree	23	100	-	-
Profession	Postgraduate degree	-	-	-	-
	Housewife	-	-	12	80
	Teachers	-	-	1	6.67
	Employee	-	-	0	-
Religion	Self-employee	-	-	2	13.34
	Islam	21	91.31	15	100
	Christian	2	8.69	0	-
	Others	-	-	-	-

3.1. Characteristics of school-friendly school

Based on the results of a questionnaire regarding the characteristics of CFS consisting of thirteen elements adopted from UNICEF, the results show that the school has indeed run a CFS model where the percentage is above 95 percent, both from the questionnaire results distributed to teachers and the class coordinator of the students' parents. This result shows that the implementation of this model is following its concept to create a school that is friendly, safe, caring, comfortable, healthy, and enjoyable without any discrimination against gender, religion, culture, and economic background. The school can realize this model, which is supported by the school principal, teachers, education staff, students' parents, and the school community. The results are shown in Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 2. The result data of teachers' response

No	Characteristics of school friendly school	Yes		No		Undecided	
		n	%	n	%	n	%
1.	Reflects and realizes the rights of every child	22	95.65			1	4.35
2.	Sees and understands the whole child, in a broad context	22	95.65	1	4.35		
3.	Child-centered	23	100				
4.	Gender-sensitive and girl-friendly	23	100				
5.	Promotes quality learning outcomes	22	95.65			1	4.35
6.	Provides education based on the reality of children's lives	23	100				
7.	Flexible and responds to diversity	22	95.65	1	4.35		
8.	Acts to ensure inclusion, respect, and equality of opportunity for all children	22	95.65	1	4.35		
9.	Promotes mental and physical health	23	100				
10.	Provides education that is affordable and accessible						
11.	Enhances teacher capacity, morale, commitment, and status	22	95.65			1	4.35
12.	Focus on family	23	100				
13.	Community-based school	23	100				

Table 3. The result data of coordinator class of students' parents

No	Characteristics of School Friendly School	Yes		No		Undecided	
		n	%	n	%	n	%
1.	Reflects and realizes the rights of every child	14	93.34			1	6.66
2.	Sees and understands the whole child, in a broad context	14	93.34			1	6.66
3.	Child-centered	14	93.34			1	6.66
4.	Gender-sensitive and girl-friendly	14	93.34	1	6.66		
5.	Promotes quality learning outcomes	15	100				
6.	Provides education based on the reality of children's lives	15	100				
7.	Flexible and responds to diversity	15	100				
8.	Acts to ensure inclusion, respect, and equality of opportunity for all children	15	100				
9.	Promotes mental and physical health	15	100				
10.	Provides education that is affordable and accessible	15	100				
11.	Enhances teacher capacity, morale, commitment, and status	15	100				
12.	Focus on family	15	100				
13.	Community-based school	15	100				

3.2. The components of child-friendly school

Aside from those above results, the school has met the requirement of the six essential components of CFS, namely pedagogy, health, inclusiveness, gender sensitivity, community participation, and protection initiated by UNICEF in different additional terms and context. In Indonesia, the implementation of child-friendly schools refers to six essential components, including: 1) Written commitment as a policy; 2) Implementation of a child-friendly learning process; 3) Well-trained teachers and personnel on children's rights; 4) Child-friendly facilities and infrastructure; 5) Children's participation; and 6) Parent participation, community institutions, business world, other stakeholders, and alumni [12], which are somewhat similar to the component by UNICEF. Thus, the research findings are based on six components in Indonesian's context. This public elementary school is regrouping of three public schools in 2016, while the CFS has been implemented since 2015. Thus, the selected principal worked hard to align with the current condition. The results of the six components are stated.

3.2.1. Component of written commitment as a policy

The first component of CFS model is written commitment as part of school policy to implement the model as it is required by Indonesian's CFS. Based on the interview with the previous and current headmasters, the school does not have a written commitment. However, all related parties understand and hold the commitment firmly. The school provides banners placed in strategic places so that all school communities can read and reflect on the meaning of child-friendly schools. Below is the statement from the former headmaster.

"The commitment is to build togetherness of all school residents, both teachers, students, parents, and students. That it is time to avoid non-violence wherever possible, instead of solving problems, violence will cause problems, both internally and externally, in the school environment. Besides, the school is labelled as a child-friendly school since no bullying and discrimination happen. So, it becomes a part of our school culture." (Previous headmaster).
"We do not pass a decree as a legal basis, but it is sufficient with the understanding that a school is regarded as a child care centre, where it must be guarded in the form of a strong mandate for education, with various forms of intelligence following students' basic

competencies. Therefore, besides learning about academics, there are also many extracurricular activities as the basis for life skills." (Current headmaster).

Not only that, but the researchers also ask about the concept of child-friendly schools to make sure whether they understand or not. Here are some interviews.

"Child-Friendly Schools are concepts that a school is conditioned as friendly, safe, comfortable, free of bullying, and reflect justice for all." (Principal).

"For me, a child-friendly school is a learning model that we as teachers must respect students' rights and provide a safe condition for all students so that the students learn without any worries." (Teacher).

"The child-friendly school is a peaceful, clean, friendly, and polite school. The teachers become friends for us." (Iren, Aura, Azra, Kaira, Students).

3.2.2. Component of a child-friendly learning process (pedagogy)

The second component is a learning process, which is similar to pedagogy in UNICEF's term. Referring to Pedagogy or a child-friendly learning process, the school implemented both the 2013 curriculum and education unit level curriculum. The 2013 curriculum has four assessment aspects, namely, aspects of knowledge, skill, attitude, and behaviour. The 2013 curriculum is an integrated curriculum that involves several disciplines to provide meaningful and broad experience to students. In other words, this curriculum emphasizes character building, which is in line with the principles of CFS about respecting.

Many activities include cooperation and collaboration among children, games, songs, storytelling, individual, and group projects. The class is arranged according to the activity, for example, when there are group activities, tables, and chairs are arranged like a round table discussion to facilitate the learning process. Children become more communicative and comfortable because of having eye contact with fellow friends in the group. As the interview was stated by some children who stated that:

"Every semester, we are asked to provide input and suggestions to the teacher regarding the learning process and activities; after that, our suggestions are posted in the classroom or school wall magazine."

Based on interviews with students in grades 4, 5, and 6, extracurricular activities are held at 1 pm every school day from Monday to Friday. Drum band extracurricular activities are held every Monday and Tuesday. Scouts are on Wednesday, dancing is on Thursday, and *Marawis* (traditional drums followed by a group of people singing Islamic songs) is on Friday. Questions raised by researchers regarding the benefits of extracurricular activities are stated below.

"I joined the band and danced because I could develop my talent." (Kaira, grade 5).

"It is exciting because I can learn a lot and be cleverer." (Azra, grade 5).

The results of observations and interviews with the Principal, Deputy Principal, Chair of the School Committee, and several children informed some routine activities carried out at this school. The routine activity is to greet the children every morning at the school gate from 06:00 to welcome them, where some assigned teachers take turns working on the activity, whereas the headmaster usually greets the children on Monday. A flag ceremony is conducted on Mondays, and doing gymnastics is on Tuesdays. On Wednesdays and Thursdays, they usually sing together in the field by singing compulsory songs such as the Indonesia Raya 3 Stanza song. On Fridays, Dhuha prayer is conducted for Muslims. For non-Muslims, they also hold worship guided by the religion teacher in the classroom.

3.2.3. Component of children participation in health aspect, learning aspect and the implementation of CFS

This public school has a school health clinic (SHC)/school public health (SPH), which provides the medicine and first aid to ill students. For health problems and children's empowerment, this school has 49 small doctors appointed by the school selected from grades 4, 5, and 6. Based on the interviews with four little appointed doctors, each of them has a duty once a week and gets a uniform. Every day there are seven little doctors on duty, whose job is to treat the sick, make tea, and provide food. Most problems that occur are fainting during ceremonies, abdominal pain, dizziness, heartburn, and falls. The doctors from the Public health centre (*Puskemas* in Indonesian term) train the students for three days about handling illness, knowledge about drugs, and knowledge about drug use. SHC also has work programs such as program

counselling, routine meetings, spatial planning, administration and data, and Trilogy of SHC covering health education, health services, and healthy school environment services. The programs and activities are well documented. Each student has to write the activities and the things that occur during their tasks as it is presented in below interviews.

"We have to make a progress report, write our activities and report it to the assigned teachers."

"I usually make a tea if a student faints during the ceremony or other injuries that happen due to the activities or playing sports." (Little doctors).

In addition to the information above, one of the manifestations of health is the existence of a healthy canteen. The concept of a healthy canteen, according to the school, is a canteen that provides food and drinks without the use of chemical dyes, MSG, and other dangerous ingredients and friendly prices. Even sellers may not sell instant noodles. The school and the parents manage two healthy canteens, where the sellers are the parents of the students and the caretaker of the school. One is a regular canteen, and the other one is a garden canteen where the head of the school committee conceived this concept to make children eat comfortably.

In terms of children's participation, children can choose extracurricular activities according to their interests and talents. They are also encouraged to report wrongdoing in the class or outside of the classroom to make sure that they understand the CFS concept. Here are a few interviews with several students during the break time in canteen.

"We are encouraged to report if the students fight or quarrel or do other bad things."

"I think there is no bullying, and discrimination in this school."

"Once we reported two male students fights during the break time and the teachers called them." (Students).

3.2.4. Component of well-trained teachers and personnel on children's rights

Well-trained teachers and personnel play a significant contribution as to implement the CFS model since they must understand the concept of CFS and children's rights. Based on the observation and interviews with teachers, and staff, they understand and implement the concept of CFS and Children's rights in the classroom. The researchers saw the good rapports and communicative interaction between teachers and students inside and outside the classroom. Here are several interviews as follows about this component.

"There is no special education for teachers and educators, but there is a psychological provision that children who are entrusted by the community as trusts must be guarded and protected and served well so that students can grow and develop in full and maximum under basic competencies. The school also informed that there was no longer any time for violence in the education environment." (Previous principal).

"The school committee and the teachers inform us about the concept of child-friendly school. Ms. Helmy (The head of the school committee) and other parents inform us that no violence, no discrimination, and no bullying are allowed in the school. Teachers also told us that we needed to respect others." (Students).

3.2.5. Component of child-friendly facilities and infrastructure

The school is a public school governed and funded by the government. Therefore, the facilities and infrastructure are similar to most of the other public schools in Indonesia. However, as the school obtains the school operational assistance funds, the principal can use the fund to improve and develop the facilities, infrastructure, and media for the learning process. So, the role of the principal is highly essential to develop the school. When we visited the school, the new principal has just been appointed for two months. During the months, there are quite many things that she has done, for example, renovating the restrooms, providing more trees and flowerpots, painting the halls, providing more extracurricular like *angklung* (traditional musical instrument). The extracurricular activities include sports (basketball, futsal), drum band, dancing, choir, scouts, and *marawis* (traditional drums followed by a group of people singing Islamic songs). Some facilities include public school health, *musholla* (praying room), library, restrooms (five for boys, eight for girls), two healthy canteens (a garden canteen and regular canteen), classrooms, Internet access, and sports arena. Here are the interviews with the principal.

“As soon as I am assigned in this school, I allocate the budget to make the school become greener by adding some flower pots and plants along the school corridors and the fields as you can see. I also have the playing field painted and buy a set of Angklung (traditional musical instrument) so the students can have more varieties of choices in music. Now I am planning to have the restrooms renovated and change some new faucets for taking wudhu next to musholla.”

3.2.6. Component of parent participation, community institutions, business world, other stakeholders, and Alumni or community participation

The last component is the participation of all parties to make sure that the school implement the CFS model, which is an important factor. The role of the school committee is also a determining factor in realizing child-friendly schools. The school committee's tasks include monitoring school activities assisted by its 47 member class coordinators, making reports for schools and a division of education sub-branches, creating work programs, assisting learning activities held outside of schools, and special events like a religious celebration. In this component, the school involves parents in mostly outdoor activities and programs.

Besides, based on interviews, the head of the committee does a lot of work efficiency in helping the school, such as the distribution of tasks with other students' parents by appointing a class coordinator, where each class has three class coordinators which aims to monitor children's development and school activities as well as planning work programs. There are 47 class coordinators manage with each other and report the progress to the chair of the committee. All those who become class coordinators are housewives who have lots of free time to help school activities more effectively and efficiently. The work program that they do routinely is doing community service which is done on Saturday or Sunday every two months; dividing tasks both for the class coordinators and children to look after and care for them, such as those in charge of the library, fish ponds, canteen, mushollah, school health clinic, fields, classes, and parks.

Public health center trains the small doctors on first aid and provides some medicine in terms of the involvement of other parties. In terms of business participation, they do not participate in managing the school and human resources. For example, Dettol sponsors the first aid and several pieces of equipment needed by the school. Some of the food companies sometimes give food and drink for the children. Also, school health clinic/school public health provided in Indonesian schools initiated by the Ministry of Health is one of the programs to support the implementation of CFS.

This article reported the implementation of the CFS model in terms of the characteristics and its components. The data above shows that the realization of the implementation of CFS in this public school has been going well according to the concept initiated by UNICEF with several different additional contexts, particularly with the six essential components. This implementation can run well for the reason that cooperation and support from all related parties. To realize the ideal child-friendly school, the local wisdom must also be adapted in each region, which is certainly different in each country. For instance, the school's extracurricular is likely different from other schools in other countries. The second difference is the welcoming greetings. The appointed teachers welcome the students in front of the school gate before entering the class and students kiss their teachers' hands, which are alike in almost all schools in Indonesia. As it is stated that CFS implementation will vary in each country as community cultural values are a more critical factor in the rule of law in realizing the global goals of the CFS approach locally [27, 28].

Research findings show that UNICEF designated for safe, caring, and child-friendly schools in South Africa has made great efforts to realize the Safe Caring Child-Friendly School (SCCFS) goals but that most of the necessary facilities in schools are inadequate due to their child-friendly status [29]. It implies that the facility has a significant impact on the realization of an ideal CFS for students. In applying the CFS model, the government must also incorporate elements of local culture in determining and developing the CFS model standard so that inconvenience arises from both teachers and students and the unpreparedness of students. Cambodia experienced the situation when the Ministry of Education began implementing the Education for All and CFS in 2006/2007 [30, 31]. Additionally, education should be improved by respecting the local cultural context [32]. Cultural understanding is fundamental and a must to achieve the outcome of an appropriate cultural project [33]. Thus, kissing teachers' hand in Indonesia, for instance, before entering the class is one of cultural differences compared to other countries.

In addition to thirteen characteristics of CFS, UNICEF requires the six important components of child-friendly schools, namely pedagogy, health, inclusiveness, gender sensitivity, community participation, and protection, while Indonesia requires six essential elements too but with different terms namely: 1) Written commitment as a policy; 2) Implementation of a child-friendly learning process; 3) Well-trained teachers and personnel on children's rights; 4) Child-friendly facilities and infrastructure; 5) Children's participation; and 6) Parent participation, community institutions, business world, other stakeholders, and alumni [12]. In other words, schools that are equipped with child-friendly characteristics are predicted to

improve the quality and variety of learning outcomes, prevent negative attitudes towards school and learning, and reduce class repetition and dropout rates. Other findings also reveal that whole-school programs involving students in different social contexts seem to reduce their experience of being bullied and increase the likelihood of telling someone if they are intimidated [34] as it is also a part of CFS model implemented in this current researched school. Thus, the appropriate curriculum in nowadays' condition brings predominantly high impacts on students' characters and attitudes. The 2013 curriculum implemented in Indonesia, based on characters and competencies that require children to be active in learning, also brings a significant influence. On the other words, it indicates that the implementation of the 2013 curriculum is aligned and harmonized with the CFS model.

Based on UNICEF, child-friendly schools are not building new schools, but conditions a school to be comfortable for children and ensures that the school fulfills the rights of children and protects it, because the school becomes a second home for children, after their own home [6]. Clair, Miske, and Patel [35] explored that CFS is a promising model for education reform, and in this way, the government can promote children's rights in many ways. Likewise, in his study, Orkodashvili [26] emphasizes that child-friendly systems can form normative goals for qualitative education and protection of children's rights. A child-friendly school is understood as a microcosm of society, where social, cultural, economic, and political dynamics, including ethnolinguistic tensions, from nations and communities, interact, collide, and be handled through rights-based approaches [35].

One of the manifestations of child-friendly schools is promoting health. As stated in the study results, this public school has implemented a healthy lifestyle and health promotion through the presence of the school health clinic, "Little Doctor," and Healthy Canteen. In Indonesia, these three things are efforts to improve the health, welfare, and quality of students that are implemented in schools from elementary school to high school. As Lohrmann [36] stated, one of the other developments of school efforts in improving health is the concept of coordinated school health. This conceptual framework emphasizes family involvement based on community needs, resources, and standards using a comprehensive healthy school approach.

In the case of stakeholder involvement, Bryan and Henry [37] have identified a positive effect on the success and discipline of student learning when stakeholders (schools, families, and community groups) participate in developing relationships. Fitriani and Istaryatiningtias [1] found that school committee and students' parents as stakeholders also play a valuable support to the implementation of CFS model. Prior research also revealed the impacts of CFS model in Jordan that is school leaders built strategies and procedures for involving parents and civic leaders in school policy, the students became more excited with the activation of their position in the learning process and the teachers began to prepare lessons and plans for the incorporation into their own classrooms of the Child Rights Conviction principles. Furthermore, in order to improve their CFS programme, stakeholders were able to use assessment tools and hopefully become agents of change [38].

Other research reveals that perceptions of school parent support and family communication have an essential role in the context of naughty behavior [39]. In terms of some forms of parental involvement opportunities, schools with increased parental participation and involvement in field activities have reduced the level of abuse [40]. The finding revealed that feeling secure in school much encourages student learning and healthy development. It was also reported that students felt insecure in large and state schools and poor high schools [41]. This finding of current study on parent participants is also similar to Song, Qian, and Goodnight's statement. Parent participation is a protective factor in schools with high racial/ethnic minorities and located in high crime sites [42]. It can be inferred that parent participation is likely able to reduce or anticipate misbehavior occurrence among students.

The most essential of the CFS implementation is the impact for students since its model emphasizes on student improvements. As the main stakeholders, students are the first individuals who feel the big differences with the learning process and school environment as to be able to express their creativity and innovation and develop their cognitive, affective and psychomotor learning domains. They also must feel comfortable, safe and enjoyable during the learning process. Thus, during the observation and interviews with parents, teachers and students, the researchers did not find any issues related to the inconvenience or behavioral issues. Some students even could express their points of views confidently without any hesitation when the researchers asked some questions related to the implementation of CFS. The research conducted in Bosnia and Herzegovina found that the implementation of CFS model gives positive impacts to several areas of students such as decision making, critical thinking, and problem-solving, self-confidence and self-respect, independence, respect for differences, teamwork skills, communication skills, academic knowledge and skills, enthusiasm for learning [43]. In addition to students' effects, Risher and Kabil also revealed that CFS had given long-term effects on principals, parents, educators, and officials at education offices all over the country. Not only that, the variables of learning environment are effective to evaluate educational programs [44, 45], which can become a part of CFS model evaluation as well.

Last but not least, the quality education is how all parties including government officials, educators, parents, and community representatives create an environment to provide students with all resources they need to meet the needs. For instance, since the students have a continuous interaction with students in a day to day basis, the role of teacher plays a significant contribution. Hattie [46] revealed that the outcomes of several studies have demonstrated that teachers play a key role in the formation of effective education. In addition, they need to create an environment to develop students' learning domains as it is stated in Bloom's taxonomy of learning in the newer version [47]. The study also revealed that teachers were keen to adopt the CFS programme, as they took an active part in it by introducing CFS concepts in their classrooms for life guidance [48]. On top of that, as a curriculum implementer, teachers need to take an active part in curriculum reforms. According to Varkey, *et al.* [49] teacher involvement in the implementation of curriculum development is helpful when assessing the achievement of such a curriculum, especially when their social resources contribute to it.

The goal of quality education is to improve development and growth of students particularly in primary schools and to equip students with the necessary life skills and social standards. Furthermore, the study indicated that the emphasis on the social-emotional wellbeing of the students seemed, in particular, to be the most important contribution to efficacy of the interventions [50]. The CFS will be surely one of the models which can provide the quality education for students' learning.

4. CONCLUSION

The characteristics and the components of CFS model are part of essential aspects in implementing its model which play beneficial contributions to students. The model of child-friendly schools is an ideology of providing a safe and protected school, trained teachers, appropriate resources, and learning environment for children. Thus, the roles of teachers and headmaster are predominantly vital to the CFS model that the need for teacher training becomes a good starting point for making schools child-friendly. Teachers and school headmaster do not merely work in these schools; they make schools child friendly and maintain the nature of schools' child-friendly atmosphere. It can be concluded that the implementation of the child-friendly school model has been going well, where the principal's leadership role, teachers and education personnel, and school committees have a positive impact on the development of schools and students. Good collaboration on all elements in implementing a child-friendly school model brings comfort, peace, security, and a better quality of life. The principles of the six important components of child-friendly schools have been fulfilled. The principles of non-discrimination, the best interests of the child, life, survival and development, respect for children's views, and good management have been taken into consideration. However, further research involving all schools need to be conducted to examine the impacts of other aspects more holistically.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The study was funded by Lembaga Penelitian dan Pengembangan (Lemlitbang), University of Muhammadiyah Prof. DR. HAMKA. Authors thank the former principal, the current principal of SDN Ragunan 01, teachers and others who supported to complete the study.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Barrow and R. Woods, *An Introduction to philosophy of education*, 4th Edition. London and New York: Routledge, 2006.
- [2] J. M. Aldridge and B. J. Fraser, "Effects and determinants of outcomes-focused learning environments," *Curric. Teach.*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 5–31, 2011.
- [3] B. J. Fraser, "Classroom learning environments," in S. K. Abell and N. G. Lederman, Eds. *Handbook of research on science education*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum, 2007, pp. 103–124.
- [4] B. J. Fraser, "Classroom learning environments: Retrospect, context and prospect," in B. J. Fraser, K. G. Tobin, and C. J. McRobbie, Eds. *Second International Handbook of Science Education*. New York: Springer, 2012, pp. 1191–1239.
- [5] L. Vermeulen and H. G. Schmidt, "Learning environment, learning process, academic outcomes and career success of university graduates," *Stud. High. Educ.*, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 431–451, 2008.
- [6] UNICEF, *The child friendly school manual*. New York: UNICEF Division of Communication, 2009.
- [7] S. Ghavifekr and N. S. Pillai, "The relationship between school's organizational climate and teacher's job satisfaction: Malaysian experience," *Asia Pacific Educ. Rev.*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 87–106, 2016.
- [8] L. Horelli, "Constructing a theoretical framework for environmental child-friendliness," *Child. Youth Environ. J.*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 267–292, 2007.

- [9] S. Porter, "Nothing but the truth? The United Nations and the Millenium Development Goals," *Policy Futur. Educ.*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 761–768, 2014.
- [10] United Nations Development Programme, "The Millennium Development Goals report 2014," New York, 2014.
- [11] E. Godfrey, *et al.*, "Cross-national measurement of school learning environments: creating indicators for evaluating UNICEF's child friendly schools initiative," *Child. Youth Serv. Rev.*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 546–557, 2012.
- [12] Kementerian Pemberdayaan Perempuan dan Perlindungan Anak Republik Indonesia, *Child friendly school guide* (in Bahasa). Jakarta: Deputi Tumbuh Kembang Anak, Kementerian Pemberdayaan Perempuan dan Perlindungan Anak Republik Indonesia, 2015.
- [13] UNICEF, "Characteristics of a rights-based, child-friendly school," UNICEF, 2012. [Online]. Available: https://www.unicef.org/lifeskills/index_7260.html. (accessed Nov. 05, 2018).
- [14] H. Küçükler, V. N. Kirtak Ad, L. Ayverdi, and S. Eğdir, "Turkish adaptation of constructivist learning environment Survey," *Elem. Educ. Online*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 671–688, 2012.
- [15] B. J. Fraser, "Learning environments research: Yesterday, today and tomorrow," in S. C. Goh and M. S. Khine, Eds. *Studies in educational learning environments: An international perspective*. Singapore: World Scientific, 2002, pp. 1–25.
- [16] A. Thapa, J. Cohen, S. Guffey, and A. Higgins-D'Alessandro, "A review of school climate research," *Rev. Educ. Res.*, vol. 83, no. 3, pp. 357–385, 2013.
- [17] M. N. Anwar, M. A. Malik, and A. Khizar, "A success story of child friendly school program: The comparative analysis," *Gomal Univ. J. Res.*, no. 4, Spec. Issue IV, pp. 65–76, 2016.
- [18] K. Bredenberg and Y. Heeyit, "The Child-friendly Schools' movement and impacts on children's learning: Practical applications in Cambodia. Working Papers: Expanded Basic Education Program," Phnom Penh, Cambodia, 2004.
- [19] F. Çobanoğlu, Z. A.- Tuncel, and A. Ordu, "Child-friendly Schools : An Assessment of Secondary Schools," *Univers. J. Educ. Res.*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 466–477, 2018.
- [20] R. E. Stake, *Qualitative research: Studying how things work*. New York, NY: The Guilford Press, 2010.
- [21] B. Gilham, *Case study research method*. London: New York: Paston PrePress Ltd., 2000.
- [22] R. K. Yin, *Case study research: design and methods*, Third ed. California: SAGE Publications Ltd., 2003.
- [23] R. K. Yin, *Case study research design and methods*, Third ed. California: SAGE Publications Ltd., 1998.
- [24] M. D. Gall, J. P. Gall, and W. R. Borg, *Educational research: An Introduction*, Eighth Ed. Boston: Pearson/Allyn & Bacon, 2007.
- [25] J. W. Creswell, *Educational research: Planning, conducting and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*, 4th ed. Boston: Pearson Education, 2012.
- [26] M. Orkodashvili, "Quality Education through Child-Friendly Schools: Resource Allocation for the Protection of Children's Rights," *Rev. Rom. pentru Educ. Multidimens.*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 101–109, 2013.
- [27] H. Özcebe, "Okul sağlığı hizmetlerinde mevcut durum ve model beklentisi. II. Ulusal Okul Sağlığı Sempozyumu Bildiri Kitabı," in J. K. Adana. Reimer, Ed. *Local negotiation of globalized educational discourses: the case of child friendly schools in rural Cambodia*, 2012.
- [28] J. K. Reimer, "Local negotiation of globalized educational discourses: The case of child friendly schools in rural Cambodia," The University of British Columbia, Vancouver, Canada, 2012.
- [29] M. C. Makwela, *et al.*, "The Intervention of Safe, Caring and Child-friendly School Policies on Social Construction of Violence in South African Secondary Schools," *J. Soc. Sci.*, vol. 50, no. 1–3, pp. 8–13, 2017.
- [30] J. B. Berkvens, "The importance of understanding culture when improving education : Learning from Cambodia," *Int. Educ. Stud.*, vol. 10, no. 9, pp. 161–174, 2017.
- [31] S. Shaeffer and K. Heng, "Child-friendly school policy implementation in Cambodia," Phnom Penh: MoEYS & Unicef Cambodia, 2016.
- [32] H. Wursten and C. Jacobs, "The impact of culture on education. Can we introduce best practices in education across countries?" 2016.
- [33] UN Sustainable Development Knowledge Platform, "Sustainable development goals, 2015," *UNITED NATIONS*, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/?menu=1300>. (accessed Feb. 13, 2020).
- [34] D. Cross, *et al.*, "Three-year results of the Friendly Schools whole-of-school intervention on children's bullying behaviour," *Br. Educ. Res. J.*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 105–129, 2011.
- [35] N. Clair, S. Miske, and D. Patel, "Child rights and quality education Child Rights and Quality Education child-friendly schools in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE)," *Eur. Educ.*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 5–22, 2016.
- [36] D. K. Lohrmann, "A complementary ecological model of the coordinated school health program," *J. Sch. Health*, vol. 80, no. 1, pp. 1–9, 2010.
- [37] J. Bryan and L. Henry, "A model for building school-family-community partnerships: Principles and process," *J. Couns. Dev.*, vol. 90, no. 4, pp. 408–420, 2012.
- [38] H. A. Weshah, O. Al-Faori, and R. M. Sakal, "Child-friendly school initiative in Jordan: A sharing experience," *Coll. Stud. J.*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 699–715, 2012.
- [39] D. B. Davalos, E. L. Chavez, and R. J. Guardiola, "Effects of Perceived Parental School Support and Family Communication on Delinquent Behaviors in Latinos and White Non-Latinos," *Cult. Divers. Ethn. Minor. Psychol.*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 57–68, 2005.
- [40] E. Lesneskie and S. Block, "School violence: The role of parental and community involvement," *J. Sch. Violence*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 426–444, 2017.
- [41] J. Devine and J. Cohen, *Making your school safe: Strategies to protect children and promote learning*. NY: Teachers College Press, 2007.

- [42] W. Song, X. Qian, and B. Goodnight, "Examining the roles of parents and community involvement and prevention programs in reducing school violence," *J. Sch. Violence*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 403–420, 2019.
- [43] M. Risher and S. Kabil, "Child friendly schools case study: Bosnia and Herzegovina," UNICEF New York, 2010.
- [44] L. M. Bell and J. M. Aldridge, *Student voice, teacher action research and classroom research (Advances in Learning Environments Research series)*, 1st ed. Rotterdam: Sense Publishers, 2014.
- [45] C. Martin-Dunlop and B. J. Fraser, "Learning environment and attitudes associated with an innovative course designed for prospective elementary teachers," *Int. J. Sci. Math. Educ.*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 163–190, 2008.
- [46] J. Hattie, *Visible learning: A synthesis of over 800 meta-analyses relating to achievement*. London, England: Routledge, 2009.
- [47] D. R. Anderson, Lorin W. Krathwohl, *A taxonomy for learning, teaching and assessing: A revision of Bloom's Taxonomy of educational objectives*. New York: Longman, 2001.
- [48] M. Modipane and M. Themane, "Teachers' social capital as a resource for curriculum development: Lessons learnt in the implementation of a Child-Friendly Schools programme," *South African J. Educ.*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 1–8, 2014.
- [49] P. Varkey, J. Peloquin, D. Reed, K. Lindor, and I. Harris, "Leadership curriculum in undergraduate medical education: A study of student and faculty perspectives," *Med. Teach.*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 244–250, 2009.
- [50] H. Korpershoek, T. Harms, H. de Boer, M. van Kuijk, and S. Doolaard, "A Meta-Analysis of the Effects of Classroom Management Strategies and Classroom Management Programs on Students' Academic, Behavioral, Emotional, and Motivational Outcomes," *Rev. Educ. Res.*, vol. 86, no. 3, pp. 643–680, 2016.